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Assessment Of Microbial Contaminants Of Selected Antimicrobial And Antipyretic Drugs Sold In Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

Antimicrobial drugs are used to treat different kinds of infectious diseases, while antipyretics are drugs used to reduce fever. However, these drugs have the potential to be contaminated by microorganisms due to poor harvesting of raw materials and inadequate hygienic practices during processing, packaging, and storage. The study aimed to describe the microbial contaminants (*Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* spp. for bacteria isolates, and *Mucor*, *Candida*, and *Penicillium* spp. for fungi isolates) of these antimicrobials (Tetracycline, Ciprofloxacin, Amoxicillin, Ketoconazole, Ketofung, and Ketoconazol) and antipyretics (Sudrex, Paracetamol, and Ibuprofen). The study purposefully selected nine samples from two different pharmacies using a laboratory research design. Microorganisms from these drugs were identified using cultural and morphological characteristics, biochemical testing (IMViC, Gram staining, and sugar fermentation), and antimicrobial susceptibility testing (disk diffusion method for bacterial isolates and agar well method for fungal isolates). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the microbial population and antimicrobial susceptibility. The mean microbial distribution of total staphylococcal counts was highest in tetracycline (8.0×10^3 CFU/g), followed by Sudrex (5.0×10^3 CFU/g) and Ibuprofen (3.3×10^3 CFU/g). The mean microbial distribution of total fungal counts was significantly found only in tetracycline (3×10^3 CFU/g). *Bacillus* spp. (8 isolates, 88.9%) and *Staphylococcus* spp. (5 isolates, 55.6%), as well as *Mucor* spp., *Candida* spp., and *Penicillium* spp., were identified across the sampled drugs. *Bacillus* spp. and *Staphylococcus* spp. showed complete resistance to cefuroxime (100%), erythromycin (100%), amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (100%), and Ceftazidime (100%). *Mucor* spp. (100%), *Candida* spp. (50%), and *Penicillium* spp. (75%) were resistant to Fluconazole. Several medication samples were found to be contaminated with microbes, likely due to improper handling, during dispensing or repackaging. This underscores the importance of adhering to proper handling procedures for pharmaceutical products.

Keywords: Microbial, Contamination, Antipyretic, Antibacterial, Antifungal drugs

INTRODUCTION

Microbial contaminants are the unintentional or accidental introduction of infectious material or their toxins into a product. Microorganisms are ubiquitous, making them prone to attack anything, even pharmaceutical products. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2017, infectious diseases accounted for about 61.7% (5.9 million) of deaths in the Sub-Saharan African Region (Tropea, 2022).

Microbial contamination of some selected antimicrobial (antibacterial, antifungal) and antipyretic drugs has been a global health problem for medical practitioners, pharmaceutical industries, and consumers of

these drugs. These drugs are chemical substances obtained naturally from plants or synthetic origins, which suppress the growth of or destroy microorganisms, including viruses, bacteria, fungi, protozoa, *etc.* (Mugoyela *et al.*, 2010).

Antimicrobial drugs are used to treat different kinds of diseases like cholera (caused by *Vibrio cholerae*), peptic ulcer (caused by *Helicobacter pylori*), tuberculosis (caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*), candidiasis (caused by *Candida albicans*), AIDS (caused by the HIV virus), *etc.* (Paphitou, 2013; Disegha and Nrior, 2021). If left untreated, these conditions can lead to sepsis. Examples of antimicrobial drugs include Ketoconazole, Clotrimazole, Nystatin, Ciprofloxacin, Ampiclox, Tetracycline, Augmentin, and Amoxicillin.

Antipyretic drugs are primarily analgesics, but they are drugs that reduce or quell fever, which, if left untreated, can lead to convulsions. Examples of antipyretic drugs are Sudrex, Ibuprofen, Anacin, and Paracetamol (Mehmood *et al.*, 2024). Pharmaceutical products are produced mainly with the aim of preventing or treating infectious diseases in humans and animals. Non-sterile preparations, although not required to pass the microbial bioburden tests and tests for the absence of certain specified indicator pathogens (European Pharmacopoeia, 2010), can still pose risks. The presence of even a low level of pathogenic microorganisms or higher levels of opportunistic or bacterial pathogens and their toxic metabolites can be fatal to immunocompromised patients, the elderly, or even infants with low immune systems (Cherry *et al.*, 2019). Our results are consistent with those of earlier studies, which discovered *Bacillus* sp. (Mugoyela and Mwambete, 2010), *Staphylococcus* sp. (Mwambete, Justin-Temu, & Fazleabbas, 2009), *Candida* sp. (Mugoyela and Mwambete, 2010; Ratajczak *et al.*, 2015), *Mucor* sp. (Ratajczak *et al.*, 2015) and *Penicillium* sp. (Ratajczak *et al.*, 2015). This contamination is a result of poor harvesting of raw materials, lack of personal hygiene, lack of sterility, contaminated environments, untreated water used during production, and issues with packaging, storing, and dispensing.

To ensure quality control, the use of aseptic techniques, proper personal hygiene, and microbial limit testing of both raw materials and finished products are essential components of a robust quality control process. Lastly, bodies governing pharmaceutical industries should ensure they are properly registered so they can monitor them from time to time to avert untimely deaths caused by microbial contaminants of antimicrobial and antipyretic drugs (Wang *et al.*, 2023).

The improvement in the healthcare system and high demand for these drugs mean that manufacturers sometimes fail to check for contaminants during drug processing, packaging, and distribution. Drugs are often derived from plants, which makes them prone to attack by microorganisms, which are ubiquitous (David *et al.*, 2015).

Most pharmaceutical industries experience annual lapses through equipment malfunction, production stoppage, drug contamination, loss of energy, and public health problems due to microbial contaminants (Eissa, 2014). In drug production industries, contaminants often come from water used during drug production, which may not be treated to remove contaminants that pose a threat to consumers' lives (Richard and Terns, 2018).

This study is geared towards bringing to light the contaminants of some antimicrobial and antipyretic drugs that might reduce their affinity, efficacy, and potency. The study will determine contaminants in some selected antimicrobial and antipyretic drugs that might bring about changes in their physicochemical characteristics. This study will directly benefit pharmacists, medical personnel, and consumers of these drugs. Through this research, the Eneka Community will be enlightened on the effects of contaminants in some selected antimicrobial and antipyretic drugs. This research is meant to add knowledge and value, and will stand as a reference point for others who intend to study the issues discussed.

The aim of this study was to investigate the level of microbial contaminants in selected antimicrobial (antibacterial, antifungal) and antipyretic drugs sold in Eneka Community, Rivers State, Nigeria. The objectives of this study are to isolate microorganisms from selected antimicrobial and antipyretic drugs; identify the bacterial and fungal loads of the selected antimicrobial and antipyretic drugs; and carry out antimicrobial susceptibility tests of contaminants in the drugs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

Samples of antifungal drugs (Ketoconazole by Hovid, Kenazol by Phamatex, Ketofung by Drug Field Pharmaceuticals), antibacterial drugs (Tetracycline by Yanzhou Pharmaceutical, Ciprofloxacin and Amoxicillin by Medreich Limited), and antipyretic drugs (Sudrex by PT. TEMPO SCAN, Paracetamol by Emzor, Ibuprofen by Me Cure) were aseptically packed in drug envelopes. They were collected from two pharmacies in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria, and transported to the Microbiology Laboratory, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt for analysis

Preparation of Media and Diluent

Various media were prepared for microbiological analysis: Nutrient Agar (NA), Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA), Salmonella Shigella Agar (SSA), Eosin Methylene Blue Agar (EMB), Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA), and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA).

Nutrient Agar (NA) was prepared by mixing 28 grams of NA powder with 1 liter of distilled water, followed by sterilization at 121°C for 15 minutes. After cooling, 10 milligrams of ketoconazole were added to the mixture, which was then poured into petri dishes and dried at 30°C. Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA) was prepared similarly, using 111 grams of MSA powder and also incorporating 10 milligrams of ketoconazole post-sterilization. For Salmonella Shigella Agar (SSA), 63 grams of SSA powder were dissolved and treated in the same manner, with ketoconazole added afterward. Eosin Methylene Blue Agar (EMB) was prepared by dissolving 35 grams of EMB powder, allowing for the growth of Gram-negative bacteria. Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) was prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions for susceptibility testing. Finally, Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) was made by mixing 65 grams of SDA with 1 liter of distilled water, with 10 milligrams of tetracycline added after sterilization to inhibit bacterial growth. For the diluent, physiological saline was created by dissolving 0.85 grams of sodium chloride in 1 liter of distilled water.

Sample Preparation

The sample drugs were pulverized and homogenized separately using a sterile mortar and pestle.

Preparation and Procedure for Serial Dilution

Serial dilutions were performed by adding 9 ml of normal saline to nine test tubes, labeled 10⁻¹ to 10⁻⁹, and autoclaved at 121°C for 15 minutes. After cooling, 1 g of each sample was added to the first tube (10⁻¹) to create a stock solution. Following this, 1 ml was pipetted from the first tube to the subsequent tubes using sterilized pipettes.

Inoculation and Incubation of Bacteria and Fungi

An aliquot of 0.1 ml from the 10⁻³ dilution was inoculated onto the surfaces of dried Nutrient Agar, Sabouraud Dextrose Agar, and Mannitol Salt Agar plates in duplicates, using a sterile 1 ml pipette. The inoculum was spread evenly with a sterile glass rod spreader. All plates were inverted and incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours for bacteria and at 20-25°C for 48-72 hours for fungi.

Enumeration and Isolation of Bacteria and Fungi Isolates

After incubating for 24-48 hours for bacteria and 48-72 hours for fungi, the colonies on the media were counted and recorded to calculate CFU/g in the sample. Morphological identification was conducted by examining colonial characteristics, including size, shape, margin, and elevation.

Identification and Characterization of Fungal Isolates

Identification and characterization of fungal isolates involved both macroscopic and microscopic examinations. For the macroscopic examination, the colonial morphology, color, texture, shape, and surface appearance were observed. In the microscopic examination, a wet preparation (needle mount) was used to assess slide culture features, including sexual and asexual reproductive structures such as sporangia and conidia heads, as well as vegetative mycelia and hyphal characteristics (septate or non-septate). A small portion of the growth was picked with a sterile inoculation needle, suspended in a drop of water on a sterile slide, and teased apart with two sterile needles. After adding lactophenol, clean cover slips were placed on the slides, ensuring no air bubbles were trapped. The prepared slides were then examined under a microscope. Reverse image identification method was used for individual identification (Disegha *et al.*, 2025).

Identification and Characterization of Bacterial Isolates

Identification of isolates was based on cultural morphology, microscopic examination, and biochemical tests, referencing Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology (1992). Morphological studies were conducted on media plates after 48 hours of growth at 30°C, focusing on colony size, shape, pigmentation, elevation, and texture to isolate pure colonies. These isolates were further characterized based on their morphological, biochemical, and physiological features as outlined by Cheesbrough (2006).

For further identification, the bacterial isolates underwent Gram staining, a critical method to determine Gram-positive (purple) or Gram-negative (red/pink) status. This involved smearing the organism on a slide, heat fixing, and applying crystal violet, followed by Lugol's iodine, decolorization with 95% ethyl alcohol, and counter-staining with safranin. The prepared slides were then examined under a microscope using a 100x objective lens with oil immersion.

Biochemical Test Analysis

Several biochemical tests were conducted to characterize the isolates.

The catalase test determined the presence of the catalase enzyme, which neutralizes hydrogen peroxide. A small colony was placed on a slide, and a drop of 3% H₂O₂ was added; bubbling indicated a positive result.

The citrate utilization test assessed the ability to use citrate as a carbon source using Simmons citrate agar. A blue coloration indicated citrate utilization.

For the sugar fermentation test, sugars like glucose and lactose were prepared with phenol red as an indicator. A color change from red to yellow and gas production in Durham tubes indicated positive results.

The indole test checked for tryptophan metabolism, with a cherry-red ring indicating a positive result after adding Kovac's reagent.

The methyl red (MR) test involved inoculating VP-MR broth; red coloration indicated a positive result.

The motility test involved inoculating semi-solid agar; growth away from the stab line indicated motility.

The oxidase test checked for cytochrome oxidase presence; purple color development indicated a positive result.

Finally, the Voges-Proskauer (VP) test assessed acetoin production, with red coloration signaling a positive outcome.

Preparation of Sensitivity Tests for Bacterial and Fungal Isolates

For bacterial isolates, the bacteria were inoculated in nutrient broth and incubated at 37°C for 5 hours. The broth was then diluted to a 0.5 McFarland turbidity standard using normal saline. A cotton swab was used to streak this diluted broth onto Mueller Hinton Agar plates. After air drying, antibiotic disks were placed 30 mm apart and 10 mm from the edges. The plates were inverted and incubated aerobically at 37°C for 16 to 18 hours, after which the zones of inhibition were measured and interpreted according to CLSI (2017) and NCCL (2002) guidelines.

For fungal isolates, Fluconazole (150 mg) was dissolved in sterile distilled water to create a 5 mg/ml concentration, followed by two-fold serial dilutions. Using the agar well diffusion method, 48-hour-old fungal cultures were swabbed on SDA plates, wells were bored, and drug concentrations were added. The plates were incubated at room temperature for 48 hours. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze microbial counts and susceptibility data.

RESULT

Microbial Population on Drug Samples

The study investigated the mean distribution of microbial populations across nine non-sterile oral drug samples, comprising three antibacterial, three antifungal, and three antipyretic drugs. As shown in Figure 1, the mean microbial distribution for total staphylococcal count was highest in tetracycline (80×10^3 CFU/g), followed by paracetamol (21×10^3 CFU/g) and kenazol (5×10^3 CFU/g). The study also revealed that the mean microbial distribution of total heterotrophic bacteria was predominantly found in paracetamol (51×10^3 CFU/g), followed by Sudrex (50×10^3 CFU/g) and ibuprofen (33×10^3 CFU/g). The mean microbial distribution of total fungi count was observed only in tetracycline (3×10^3 CFU/g).

Figure 1: Mean Distribution of Microbial Population across the drug samples

Key: AB1: Tetracycline; AB2: Ciprofloxacin; AB3: Amoxicillin; AF1: Ketoconazole; AF2: Kenazol; AF3: Ketofungi; APY2: Paracetamol; APY3: Ibuprofen.

The fungal isolates were identified based on their macroscopic and microscopic characteristics (Table 1). Isolate A exhibited a fluffy white cottony appearance with a white reverse and was identified microscopically as having aseptate hyphae bearing round sporangiospores, indicating it is *Mucor sp.* Isolate B presented as a cream-colored, small, round raised colony, with microscopic examination revealing spherical budding cells, suggesting it is *Candida sp.* Finally, Isolate C had a green powdery surface surrounded by a white lawn and a brown reverse; its microscopic analysis showed septate hyphae with conidiophores bearing conidia, leading to its identification as *Penicillium sp.*

Table 1: Macroscopy and Microscopy of Fungal Isolates

Isolates	Macroscopy	Microscopy	Probable Identity
A.	Fluffy white cottony, white reverse	Aseptate hyphae bearing round sporangiospores	<i>Mucor sp.</i>
B.	Cream small round raised colony	Spherical budding cells	<i>Candida sp.</i>
C.	Green powdery surface surrounded by white lawn, brown reverse	Septate hyphae with septate conidiophores bearing conidia	<i>Penicillium sp.</i>

Based on morphological presentation on petri dishes, bacterial isolates for Total Heterotrophic Bacterial count (THB) and Total Staphylococcal Count (TSC) exhibited rough, smooth, golden, yellow, flat, slightly raised, small, and large colonies. Microscopy (Table 3) revealed that *Bacillus* species constituted 8 (88.9%) of the isolates across the drug samples, while *Staphylococcus* species constituted 5 (55.6%), with both rod and cocci shapes observed. Biochemical analysis (Table 2) presented a series of results, indicating both positive and negative reactions for different biochemical parameters. The most suspected organisms were *Bacillus sp.* and *Staphylococcus sp.* For fungal isolates identified across the drug samples, as shown in Table 4, the suspected fungi were *Mucor sp.*, *Candida sp.*, and *Penicillium sp.*, identified according to their macroscopic characteristics.

Table 2: Cultural Characteristics and Morphology of Bacterial Isolates

Isolate	Shape	Gram	Motility	Catalase	Indole	Oxidase	MR	VP	Sucrose	Mannit	Glucose	Fructose	Citrate	Lactose	Identity
1	Cocci	+ve	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>
2	Rod	+ve	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Bacillus sp.</i>

Table 3 outlines the distribution pattern of bacterial isolates across various drug samples. The isolates studied include *Staphylococcus sp.* and *Bacillus sp.* For *Staphylococcus sp.*, positive occurrences were noted with Tetracycline, Ketoconazole, Kenazol, and Paracetamol, resulting in an overall occurrence rate of 55.6%. In contrast, *Bacillus sp.* showed positive reactions to Tetracycline, Amoxyl, Ketoconazole, Kenazol, and Ketofungi, with a higher occurrence rate of 88.9%. Both bacterial isolates tested negative

for Ciprofloxacin and Ibuprofen, while *Staphylococcus sp.* also had negative results with Amoxyl and Ketofungi, and *Bacillus sp.* was negative for Ketoconazole.

Table 3: Distribution Pattern of Bacterial Isolates across the Drug Samples

Isolate	<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	<i>Bacillus sp.</i>
Tetracycline	+	+
Ciprofloxacin	-	-
Amoxyl	-	+
Ketoconazole	+	+
Kenazol	+	+
Ketofungi	-	+
Paracetamol	+	+
Ibuprofen	-	+
% Occurrence	55.6	88.9

Antibiotic and Antifungal Susceptibility Testing

Antibiotic susceptibility testing for bacterial isolates was carried out using the disk diffusion method, as illustrated in Table 4. Results showed that *Bacillus sp.* was highly resistant to cefuroxime (100%) and ceftazidime (100%). The study also indicated that *Staphylococcus sp.* was highly resistant to ceftriaxone (100%), erythromycin (100%), amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (100%), and ceftazidime (100%). Antifungal susceptibility for fluconazole, using the agar well method, demonstrated that *Mucor sp.* (100%), *Candida sp.* (50%), and *Penicillium sp.* (75%) were resistant to fluconazole.

Table 5 presents the antifungal susceptibility test results for Fluconazole and Ketoconazole across different fungal isolates.

Mucor sp. was resistant to both Fluconazole and Ketoconazole, indicated by a zone size of less than 14 mm for both drugs. In contrast, *Candida sp.* was sensitive to Fluconazole (zone size ≥ 18 mm) and also sensitive to Ketoconazole (zone size ≥ 16 mm). *Penicillium sp.* displayed intermediate susceptibility to Fluconazole, with a zone size between 15 and 17 mm, while it was sensitive to Ketoconazole, with a zone size of 16 mm or greater.

Table 4: Antimicrobial susceptibility results with zone sizes (in mm) for the *Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* Species

Bacteria	<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	<i>Bacillus sp.</i>
Tetracycline	22	18
Ciprofloxacin	28	30
Amoxicillin	12	16
Cefuroxime	17	20
Gentamicin	21	24
Cloxacillin	15	17
Erythromycin	16	15
Ceftriaxone	25	23
Ofloxacin	27	29
Amoxicillin	23	21
Ceftazidime	19	22

Key: CLSI STANDARS: 1. Tetracycline (Susceptible: ≤ 15 mm; Intermediate: 16-20 mm; Resistant: ≥ 21 mm), 2. Ciprofloxacin (Susceptible: ≤ 21 mm; Intermediate: 22-26 mm; Resistant: ≥ 27 mm), 3. Amoxicillin (Susceptible: ≤ 18 mm; Intermediate: 19-23 mm; Resistant: ≥ 24 mm) (CLSI, 2017).

Table 5: Antifungal Susceptibility of Fluconazole and Ketoconazole in Various Fungal Isolates

Fungi Species	Fluconazole (Zone Size: S/I/R)	Ketoconazole (Zone Size: S/I/R)
<i>Mucor sp.</i>	R: Zone size < 14 mm	R: Zone size < 14 mm
<i>Candida sp.</i>	S: Zone size ≥ 18 mm	S: Zone size ≥ 16 mm
<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	I: Zone size 15-17 mm	S: Zone size ≥ 16 mm

DISCUSSION

Pharmaceuticals are used in various ways for disease diagnosis, treatment, and prevention. Recent quality improvements by pharmaceutical producers have led to non-sterile medications having only a minor bioburden (Mugoyela, Mugoyela & Mwambete, 2010). This study aimed to describe the microbial contaminants present in selected antimicrobial and antipyretic drugs sold in Eneka, Rivers State.

The study results indicated that most of the tested drug samples, with the exception of Ciprofloxacin, were microbiologically contaminated. *Bacillus* sp. and *Staphylococcus* sp. were the predominant aerobic bacteria isolated, while *Candida* sp., *Mucor* sp., and *Penicillium* sp. were the main fungal contaminants. These findings align with earlier studies that identified *Bacillus* sp. (Mugoyela and Mwambete, 2010), *Staphylococcus* sp. (Mwambete, Justin-Temu and Fazleabbas, 2009), *Candida* sp. (Mugoyela, Mugoyela & Mwambete, 2010; Ratajczak et al., 2015), and *Penicillium* sp. (Ratajczak et al., 2015) as major microbial contaminants in non-sterile pharmaceuticals. Notably, the current investigation found that the bioburden in these samples was up to ten times greater than the permitted limits (100 CFU/ml) (Yang, Li and Chang, 2013).

Eight contaminated samples (89.9%) of oral drugs were observed, with exceeded limits of aerobic microorganisms primarily found in antipyretic drugs. The highest bacterial count was recorded in paracetamol (51×10^3 CFU/gg), followed by Sudrex (50×10^3 CFU/gg). The highest fungal contamination, found in only one sample (tetracycline), was 3.0×10^3 CFU/g. These findings are consistent with earlier reports showing a highest mold contamination of 3.4×10^3 CFU/g and a highest bacterial contamination of 160×10^3 CFU/g (Ratajczak et al., 2015). This widespread contamination signals that stricter precautions are necessary and highlights improper handling practices within our pharmacies.

Most of the bacteria identified from the samples belong to the common human flora, which are ubiquitous in nature (Ekhaise, Isitor and Idehen, 2011). This suggests that microbiological contamination of these medications is a result of inappropriate handling, lax hygienic practices during repacking into smaller packets, and improper administration of pharmaceuticals. The danger posed by potentially pathogenic opportunistic microorganisms, such as *Staphylococcus* sp., *Bacillus* sp., and *Candida* sp., to patients' health cannot be overstated. This is particularly true for adults with weakened immune systems and infants with underdeveloped immune systems (Carolus, Van Dyck, and Van Dijck, 2019). Given the global prevalence of drug resistance, the observed drug-resistant microbial contaminants in this study underscore the urgent need for immediate and more stringent measures to address the situation by adhering to rational antibiotic usage in our communities. Ingesting such drug-resistant microorganisms can aggravate illness in individuals with suppressed immune systems due to secondary infections (Carolus, Van and Van Dijck, 2019; Centre for Disease Control (CDC), 2019). Pathogenic microorganisms become problematic when they outnumber the normal flora, leading to health problems (Ekhaise, Isitor and Idehen, 2011). The microbiological quality of non-sterile medication is significantly influenced by the bioburden of raw materials, including active components and excipients (Ratajczak et al., 2015). Therefore, a failure to strictly adhere to good manufacturing practices at any stage of production can profoundly impact the microbiological quality of finished products (Ratajczak et al., 2015). This is further exacerbated in countries with tropical climates like Nigeria, where environmental conditions make poorly stored pharmaceuticals susceptible to microbial spoilage (Mugoyela and Mwambete, 2010).

In terms of susceptibility testing, the isolated bacteria (*Bacillus* sp. and *Staphylococcus* sp.) were found to be highly resistant to Cefuroxime, Cloxacillin, Erythromycin, Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (Augmentin), Ceftazidime, and Ceftriaxone. The failure of Augmentin to act as a β -lactamase enzyme inhibitor is a significant concern, as both *Bacillus* sp. and *Staphylococcus* sp. can develop extended-spectrum β -lactamases and be methicillin-resistant (Donkor and Codjoe, 2019).

Although the isolated *Candida* sp. was found to be slightly susceptible to Fluconazole, it remains an opportunistic pathogen known to cause potentially fatal health deterioration in immunocompromised individuals (Ekhaise, Isitor and Idehen, 2011).

Therefore, adherence to aseptic techniques during pharmaceutical preparation, along with proper training and educating personnel on personal hygiene, can significantly reduce microbial cross-contamination. This in turn, helps prevent product spoilage and safeguards patients from health risks.

CONCLUSION

This study reveals significant microbial contamination in selected antimicrobial and antipyretic drugs sold in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, with total staphylococcal and heterotrophic bacterial counts often exceeding permissible limits. *Bacillus* and *Staphylococcus* species were the most prevalent bacterial contaminants, while *Mucor*, *Candida*, and *Penicillium* species dominated fungal contamination. Critically, these isolated bacterial species demonstrated high rates of resistance to commonly used antibiotics, including cefuroxime, erythromycin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, and ceftazidime. Furthermore, significant resistance to fluconazole was observed among the fungal isolates. These findings underscore a substantial public health risk, suggesting that inadequate handling, storage, and dispensing practices contribute to compromised drug quality and could potentially lead to adverse patient outcomes, including the propagation of antimicrobial resistance within the community.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Pharmaceutical manufacturers, distributors, and retailers must collectively reinforce Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) (2013) and Good Distribution Practices (GDP) throughout the supply chain. This includes rigorous quality control checks on raw materials, implementation of stringent aseptic techniques during drug production and packaging, and maintaining optimal storage conditions that prevent microbial growth, especially in tropical climates like Nigeria. Regular and unannounced audits by regulatory bodies should be conducted to ensure continuous compliance and to identify and rectify any lapses in hygiene and processing that could lead to contamination.

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